

Reactions of Sodium Nitrite with Mineral Acids

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If mineral acids simply displaced sodium from sodium nitrite, the reaction would be

This is realised when the air has been removed by a current of CO_2 . When H_2 is used for removal (conventional hydrogen electrode), the acid required is 10-20% too low; in the reverse titration, the nitrite required is about 10% too high. The acid required is 2% too low at low initial concentration of NaNO_2 in the cell, but at higher concentrations it is again 20% too low when an air electrode is used. The errors are much worse in the reverse titration. The results improve remarkably when urea is present (air electrode) and are stoichiometric when KI has been added to the cell.

These results may be explained if it is assumed that nitrite ions may be oxidised by oxygen to nitrate ions in presence of free nitrous acid and hydrogen ions.

The displacement of HNO_2 from an alkali nitrite by the action of mineral acids may be treated as a simple neutralisation process in which the anion base NO_2^- is neutralised by H^+ :

Such displacement titrations can be performed satisfactorily if the ionisation constant of the weak acid displaced¹ is less than 10^{-6} . In such cases a rapid change in pH is expected near the equivalence point. Several such titrations have been reported by earlier workers². Hildebrand also obtained several displacement titration curves in course of his studies on the use of the hydrogen electrode. Pinkhof³ performed satisfactory potentiometric titrations of acetates with HCl (hydrogen electrode) and obtained good results only when concentration of the acetates was greater than $1N$.

Little attention appears to have been paid towards the potentiometric titration of an alkali nitrite with mineral acids. Müller and Dachselt⁴ performed a potentiometric titration of the acid solution of an aromatic amine with sodium nitrite and found a jump in the potential at the equivalence point. A few other similar titrations have been also reported⁵.

The ionisation constant of HNO_2 is 4×10^{-4} , a value too high to allow an appreciable break in pH -neutralisation curve, and a successful titration appears unlikely. It is well

1. Glasstone, "Introduction to Electrochemistry", p. 396, D. Van Nostrand, N. Y.
2. Kolthoff and Stenger, "Volumetric Analysis", Part II, p. 150.
3. Dissertation, Amsterdam, 1919, p. 44.
4. *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1925, 31, 662.
5. *Chem. Abst.*, 1953, 47, 7935^g.

known that HNO_2 may be oxidised to HNO_3 so that there is a possibility of a suitable redox electrode set up for a good titration. Preliminary experiments showed that quite steep inflections were actually obtained in the titration of nitrite with mineral acid with the help of a platinum electrode.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were all of A.R. quality. A stock solution of 2M- NaNO_2 was prepared from which solutions of lower concentrations were made when required. These were standardised from time to time with standard KMnO_4 solutions. Standard solutions of HCl and H_2SO_4 were also prepared. In order to carry out a potentiometric titration, a known volume (10 or 25 ml) of the solution to be titrated was taken in a small Pyrex beaker and the other solution added from a burette. A Pt-foil electrode was used under conditions specified below. The other half-cell was a saturated calomel electrode (KCl-agar bridge) and the E.M.F. was measured on a stretched-wire potentiometer⁶. All the titrations were performed at room temperature (25-30°). The results are recorded in Tables I-IV.

TABLE I
Conventional hydrogen electrode.

(a) 25ml of x molar NaNO_2 in cell; y molar HCl .

No.	x .	y .	Expected.	Found.	% Dif.
1	2.00	4.0600	12.3 ml	10.1 ml	-18.3
2	1.00	2.0300	"	10.4	-15.4
3	0.50	1.0150	"	11.0	-10.5
4	0.10	0.5075	"	10.8	-12.2

(b) 25ml of y molar HCl in cell; x molar NaNO_2 .

5	2.00	1.9610	13.25	14.90	11.7
6	1.00	0.5075	12.68	14.10	11.2
7	0.50	0.2537	12.68	13.90	9.8
8	0.25	0.1015	10.15	10.90	7.4

Indicator Electrode

Except in the experiments, results of which are given in Table I, a bright platinum foil electrode was used in these titrations. In some of them the solutions were left fully saturated with air so that the assembly could be regarded as an air electrode⁷. It is not possible to use quinhydrone electrode to follow the pH changes in these titrations since addition of nitrite to quinhydrone leads to a gradual darkening of the solution.

The conventional hydrogen electrode was used in the titrations recorded in Table I. For those in Table IV, a steady stream of purified CO_2 was passed in place of hydrogen and the foil was not platinised.

With sufficiently dilute solutions, no brown fumes were observed. The trouble set in when one of the solutions was concentrated.

6. Gyani and Prasad, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 313.

7. Kolthoff and Laitinen, "pH and Electro-titrations", p. 97, John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York; Van Meulen and Wilcox, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 62.

TABLE II

Air electrode.

(a) 10ml x molar NaNO_2 in cell; y molar HCl .

No.	x .	y .	Expected.	Found.	%Diff.
1	0.050	1.252	1.98 ml	1.95 ml	- 1.5
2	0.484	1.008	4.80	4.40	- 8.0
3	0.484	1.800	2.68	2.30	-11.1
4	1.000	3.600	2.73	2.50	-10.0
5	1.000	5.190	1.92	1.45	-24.4
6	1.000	7.091	1.40	1.10	-21.4

(b) 10ml x molar NaNO_2 in cell; y molar H_2SO_4 .

7	0.10	0.200	5.00	4.90	- 2.0
8	0.50	0.775	6.45	4.85	-24.8
9	0.50	1.562	3.20	2.68	-17.1
10	1.00	2.530	3.05	2.85	-27.1
11	1.00	4.060	2.46	1.90	-22.7

(c) 10 ml y molar HCl in cell; x molar nitrite.

12	1.00	0.090	0.900	1.30	44.4
13	1.00	0.150	1.560	2.10	34.4
14	2.00	0.156	0.780	0.95	21.6
15	2.00	0.775	3.875	4.80	23.9

Some of the corresponding graphs will be found in Figs. 1-3. Although the inflections are steep, there are large deviations from the expected values. The acid requirement corresponding to the inflection is always less than the calculated value whether one starts

with nitrite or acid in the cell. The only satisfactory result has been obtained when a dilute ($M/20$) nitrite is taken in the cell and the air electrode is used (Table II). An acid stronger than HNO_2 is surely produced in these titrations.

FIG. 3

Pick⁸ has assumed that the following ionic equilibrium exists in nitrite solutions:

Hence the loss of nitrite ions may be followed by dipping a bright platinum electrode and adding a little nitrate in the beginning to help a rapid attainment of equilibrium. When titrations were carried out in this manner, only five minutes were required for equilibrium and the results were considerably improved (cf. Table III). This lends support to the view that in these titrations we are following an oxidation potential other than that involved in

There are two reactions which are relevant to nitrite solutions. The first is the production of NO from HNO_2 in presence of hydrogen ions:

This is perhaps the reaction which takes place when solutions, which are not dilute, are used. Oxygen is not required. We can also think of another reaction, an oxygen-consuming reaction, when there is a fair concentration of nitrite ions. Since the nitrite ion has no proton to lose, the first steps may be the formation of an intermediate compound,

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$\text{NO}_2^- \text{H}^+$. We must find a base in the system and the most likely one is

This reaction cannot proceed unless both oxygen and free HNO_2 are present. If one or both of these are removed and if conditions are so chosen that reaction (iii) is minimised, it is likely that quite satisfactory titrations of nitrites and mineral acids are possible. With these ideas in mind we carried out three more sets of titrations in spite of the fact that titration with conventional hydrogen electrode (air-free system) did not produce encouraging results earlier.

TABLE III

Sodium nitrate present.
10ml of x molar NaNO_2 in cell; y molar HCl .

No.	x .	y .	Expected.	Found.	%Diff.
1	0.05	0.25	2.00 ml	2.00 ml	0.0
2	0.45	1.81	2.48	2.43	- 2.0
3	0.90	3.40	2.63	2.50	- 4.9
4	1.00	1.81	5.50	4.75	-13.6
5	2.00	3.63	5.50	4.65	-15.4

In the first, oxygen was removed by bubbling CO_2 ; in the second, a little urea was added to the cell and in the third, KI was added. The results are summarised in Tables IV-VI. Nitrous acid is destroyed by iodide⁹ thus:

TABLE IV

System made air-free by bubbling CO_2 .
10ml of x molar NaNO_2 in cell; y molar HCl .

No.	x .	y .	Expected.	Found.	%Diff.
1	0.10	0.289	3.50 ml	3.46 ml	-1.15
2	2.25	1.040	2.40	2.35	-2.10
3	0.50	2.092	2.40	2.39	-0.40
4	1.00	2.092	4.78	4.65	-2.70
5	2.00	4.160	4.80	4.50	-4.10

TABLE V

Urea added to the cell.
10ml x molar NaNO_2 in cell with 6ml N -urea hydrochloride; y molar HCl .

No.	x .	x .	y .	Expected.	Found.	%Diff.
1	0.5	0.5	1.08	9.39ml	8.50 ml	-8.5
2	1.0	1.0	2.14	4.67	4.45	-4.3
3	2.0	2.0	2.15	9.30	8.50	-8.5

9. Sneed and Brasted, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", p. 61, Van Nostrand, N.Y.

TABLE VI

KI added to the cell.

10ml x molar NaNO_2 in cell; y molar HCl ; $z = \text{ml } M/1 - \text{KI}$.

No.	x .	y .	Expected.	Found.	z .	%Diff.
1	1.00	2.00	10.00	9.85	15.0	-1.5
2	0.50	0.85	11.76	11.70	7.0	-0.8
3	0.25	0.50	10.00	10.10	3.0	-1.0
4	0.10	0.50	4.00	3.95	1.5	-1.2
5	0.50	0.50	20.00	20.50	5.5	+2.5(?)

DISCUSSION

The results in Tables IV and VI are very satisfactory. These definitely establish that when oxygen is effectively excluded or a substance is present which removes HNO_2 as soon as it is formed, equation (i) is followed and the reaction is primarily a simple displacement one. The removal of HNO_2 by urea may not be rapid enough and some oxidation in accordance with equation (iii) may take place. It is also clear that at least in solutions, not stronger than 1 M , reaction (ii) is practically inoperative.

Referring again to reaction (ii), we can see that only one-third of the nitrite will be neutralised by the HNO_3 formed in the cell. According to reaction (iii) only half the nitrite requires external acid. Thus, the maximum error will be -33.3% and -50% respectively.

The maximum deviations are found in Table II, No. 12 and 13. 0.9ml of $N/1$ - HCl will produce 0.45ml of $N/1$ - HNO_3 if the reaction (iii) is quantitatively operative, requiring 1.35ml of $N/1$ nitrite against 1.30ml actually observed. The deviation becomes less in high initial concentrations of HCl . It appears that in these subsequent titrations some nitrite is lost as NO in accordance with reaction (ii). If reaction (ii) alone were operative, one would have one-third more nitrite consumed than the quantity of acid present. Thus in No. 13, 1.56ml of $N/1$ acid initially present would consume 2.08ml of $N/1$ nitrite against 2.10ml actually observed. The results of Table II (c) are not as ill-behaved as they appear at first sight. It may be realised that in these titrations the $p\text{H}$ is increasing all the while. It is possible that by starting with HCl , more dilute than 0.09 N in Table II (c), a strict adherence to reaction (iii) may be secured.

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